

The Innovation Challenge Design Canvas

Challenge Name _____

WHY?	WHAT?	HOW?
<p>1. GOAL</p> <p>Innovation Challenges are ran to support Open Innovation in SMEs. However, an innovation agency may also wish to achieve specific strategic goals via a Challenge. For example, a Challenge could be expected to impact both SMEs and other participants. Clarifying these strategic aspects at the very beginning is crucial in order to avoid problems down the road.</p>		
<p>2. SEEKERS</p> <p>Seekers are organizations (maybe more than one) that are facing one or more innovation problems and looking for answers. These might be the SMEs you want to support, or even Larger Enterprises (LE) you want to connect with SMEs. The seeker acts as "the client" of the initiative: the one who defines a specific problem or opportunity, and hopes to find some form of innovation via the Challenge.</p>		
<p>3. CHALLENGE</p> <p>This is the innovation issue that entices seekers to take part to the Innovation Challenge. It could be a technical problem with a production process, a design problem related to the development of a new product, or an aspect of business. A challenge may also offer an opportunity. The challenge is what solvers will actively work on in their "problem solving" activities.</p>		
<p>4. SOLUTIONS</p> <p>This is the usable value-adding result that the seeker hopes to obtain from the Challenge, which should be the solution to the innovation problem submitted by the seeker, or significant progress towards its solution. It is the main motivation for seekers taking part in the Challenge, and something they are prepared to pay for.</p>		